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Factors Affecting Entrepreneurial Inclination Among Angolan Students in the Philippines: Basis for Entrepreneurship Education and Training in Angola

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the factors influencing entrepreneurial inclination among a stratified sample of 56 Angolan students in the Philippines. Utilizing a quantitative approach, data were collected via questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson correlations. Results indicated no significant relationship between student demographics and entrepreneurial inclination. However, a positive correlation was found between entrepreneurial inclination and both the university's role in promoting entrepreneurship and the perceived relevance of the entrepreneurial curriculum. The perceived relevance of the curriculum emerged as the strongest predictor of student engagement. These findings suggest that universities can positively influence students' entrepreneurial aspirations through targeted curricular interventions. Further research is needed to explore these relationships in other contexts.

KEYWORDS: Entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurship inclination, Angola,

INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurship is recognized by policymakers and researchers as a key determinant of economic growth, employment generation, innovation, and poverty reduction, particularly in the context of African economies (Apetu et al., 2025; Brixiova & Kangoye, 2014). Entrepreneurs exert a significant influence on societal structures through the introduction of new products and the transformation of established practices (Hui et al., 2015). Globally, entrepreneurial activity is on the rise, playing an increasingly important role in the international business environment, and aligning with a strengthened emphasis on private-sector development initiatives (Geldhof et al., 2014).

Institutions of higher education are increasingly recognized as primary sources for cultivating well-educated, entrepreneurial talent (Matlay, 2010, 2011). Graduate and student entrepreneurs, therefore, represent a significant national resource, possessing the capacity to instigate substantive socioeconomic change (Radovic & Salamzadeh, 2012). Consequently, the deliberate cultivation of entrepreneurship within higher education is critical for facilitating sustained socioeconomic advancement.

The significance of the entrepreneur's role in society is widely acknowledged by economists, behavioral scientists, and policymakers alike. Entrepreneurs are frequently credited with driving economic development through the introduction and implementation of innovative concepts (Ranjan, 2016), encompassing product, process, market, and organizational innovations. Concomitant with the increasing recognition of the entrepreneur and entrepreneurship as fundamental components of economic development, the study of entrepreneurial inclination has also gained considerable importance (Cozzarin, 2017). Entrepreneurial inclination encompasses the intellectual, behavioral, and attitudinal predispositions that influence an individual's propensity to start a business or enterprise.

The personality characteristics and demographic attributes of the entrepreneur are posited to exert a crucial influence on the success of entrepreneurial ventures. Indeed, recent research (Pinelli, 2012) suggests the existence of discernible differences in personality traits between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. These differentiating factors may include gender, religious affiliation, age, field of academic study, prior work experience, and the occupational backgrounds of parents.

Governments worldwide face the persistent challenge of reducing youth unemployment, necessitating targeted strategies for employment creation. In 2013, an estimated 74.5 million young people aged 15–24 were unemployed, an increase of approximately one million from the previous year. The International Labor Organization (2014) indicates a global youth unemployment rate of 13.1 percent. Recognizing entrepreneurship as a fundamental element of economic development, it is crucial to understand the factors that influence young people's inclination towards entrepreneurial pursuits. Consequently, assessing the entrepreneurial inclination of university students, who represent a vital pool of future entrepreneurs, is of paramount importance. Furthermore, investigating the factors that can enhance this inclination is imperative for fostering economic growth and opportunity.

Entrepreneurship education aims to cultivate entrepreneurial understanding, intentions, and behaviors in students, ultimately leading to the creation of new businesses and employment opportunities (Fayolle & Gailly, 2005; Ly, 2021). Identifying students' entrepreneurial characteristics and their relationship to entrepreneurial inclination can significantly contribute to addressing unemployment and fostering graduate entrepreneurship (Ibidunni et al., 2020). Furthermore, research has suggested a relationship between entrepreneurial inclination and demographic and family business background variables (Rengiah & Sentosa, 2014). This study aimed to address the identified gaps by examining the entrepreneurial inclination of Angolan students in business management departments at several schools in the Philippines, thereby contributing to a more nuanced understanding of the factors influencing entrepreneurship in this specific context.

Roxas (2014) emphasizes the importance of cultivating entrepreneurial knowledge as a foundation for nurturing students' self-confidence and attitudinal predisposition towards engaging in entrepreneurial activities. This perspective aligns with Mensah's (2013) assertion that educational institutions, particularly schools and universities, play a crucial role in promoting entrepreneurship. The institutions are ideally positioned to shape entrepreneurial cultures and aspirations among students, preparing them to thrive in today's dynamic business environment (Al-Fattal, 2024; Bozkurt & Alparslan, 2012; Moriano et al., 2012). Liu and Yao-Ping Peng (2025) posited that universities, therefore, play a significant role in fostering students' entrepreneurial careers and inclinations. The learning environment within universities exerts a considerable influence on students' perceptions of entrepreneurial career development and their likelihood of pursuing independent ventures (Zhang et al., 2014; Liñan et al., 2011; Valencia-Arias, 2022). The entrepreneurship curriculum within universities has been identified as a critical factor in providing students not only with knowledge but also with essential skills, training, and effective learning models (Igwe et al., 2021; Oyugi, 2014; Sheta, 2012). Furthermore, entrepreneurship is a multifaceted phenomenon that varies depending on the specific context, the level of innovation involved, and the overall impact on society (Betomol, 2021; Griffiths et al., 2012). Welter (2011) argued that adopting a contextual perspective on entrepreneurship enhances our understanding of this complex phenomenon, highlighting the importance of considering when, how, and why entrepreneurship occurs, as well as who becomes involved.

Extensive research has been conducted in recent years to assess the entrepreneurial inclinations of university students (Anwar & Saleem, 2019; Aktürk, 2012; Asamani & Mensah, 2013; Armağan, 2013; Arrighetti et al., 2013; Bozkurt & Alparslan, 2012; Çelik, et al., 2014; Demireli et al., 2014; Koçyiğit, 2013; Moriano et al., 2012; Rani, 2012; Ridzuan, 2021; Şeşen & Basım, 2012; Tong et al., 2011; Yumuk, 2013). However, a review of this literature reveals a notable gap in the population and methodology: the majority of studies have not focused on students from Business Management Departments, nor have they specifically examined the context of Angolan students. While some research has explored the entrepreneurial attitudes of students in Business Management Departments (Cachon & Cotton, 2008; Farrington et al., 2012; Doğan, 2013), the existing literature remains limited.

The participants in this study were Angolan students currently pursuing higher education in the Philippines (from 2010 to 2018). In a developing context such as Angola, entrepreneurship development plays a pivotal role in fostering self-employment and mitigating unemployment, making it even more critical than in developed economies. Although Angola possesses abundant natural and human resources, the nation has yet to achieve its desired growth trajectory—largely due to the inefficient management and underutilization of these resources, corruption, and questionable government. Despite being one of Africa's leading oil producers, Angola continues to grapple with the socioeconomic aftermath of a 27-year civil war that followed independence. The resulting economic expansion has not translated into broad-based prosperity; approximately two-thirds of Angolans continue to live on less than two dollars per day, reflecting a significant gap between national growth and individual well-being (Cassinela & Cacknazarof, 2024).

This research draws primarily on the study by Keat et al. (2011), which examined key determinants of entrepreneurial inclination, including perceptions of entrepreneurship, exposure to role models, the university's role in promoting entrepreneurship, curriculum content, independent learning approaches, and entrepreneurial internship experiences. The study also examined the relationship between demographic variables, family business backgrounds, and entrepreneurial inclination, offering a valuable framework for understanding the entrepreneurial aspirations of university students in the Philippines. Figure 1 shows the proposed conceptual framework for the study.

Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1: A Conceptual Framework for Entrepreneurial Inclination

In the community college context, it is crucial to present students with a positive image of entrepreneurship as a viable career path by providing them with appropriate resources and facilities (Miao, 2021). Even when individuals possess business knowledge and skills, a negative perception of entrepreneurship may hinder them from pursuing entrepreneurial ventures (Alberti et al., 2004; Zhao et al., 2021).

Entrepreneurial role models motivate, inspire, and support students' aspirations (Bosma et al., 2012). Exposure to role models—whether through positive or negative experiences—encourages individuals to assess their entrepreneurial potential (Lavolette et al., 2012). Role models thus play a vital role in shaping entrepreneurial careers by offering information, guidance, and moral support (Postigo et al., 2006; Rajkonwar, 2006), making entrepreneurial success more attainable and relatable (Bygrave, 2004; Keat, 2011).

Universities and schools play a crucial role in fostering entrepreneurial education and promoting economic development (Binks et al., 2006; Co & Mitchell, 2006). As centers for cultivating entrepreneurial culture and aspiration, educational institutions serve as seedbeds for innovation and entrepreneurial thinking (Mahlberg, 1996; Landström, 2005; Keat, 2011; Bygrave, 2004). An independent learning approach is equally critical. Entrepreneurship education should extend beyond classroom instruction to include experiential learning, as entrepreneurial skills are best developed through practice (Dilts & Fowler, 1999; McIntyre & Roche, 1999; Cooper et al., 2004; Keat, 2011).

Demographic and family background factors—such as gender, religion, age, field of study, work experience, and parents' occupations—also influence entrepreneurial outcomes (Pinelli, 2012). Finally, while entrepreneurial inclination and potential entrepreneurship are often discussed together, they differ conceptually. Inclination refers to a general tendency toward entrepreneurship, whereas intention denotes a concrete commitment to pursue a business opportunity (Krueger & Brazeal, 1994; Ashcroft et al., 2004).

The study by Keat et al. (2011) found that the university's role in promoting entrepreneurship, as well as entrepreneurial curriculum and content, gender, work experience, and mother's occupation, were significant predictors of entrepreneurial inclination. These findings underscore the importance of universities in fostering entrepreneurial ecosystems through innovative curricula and experiential learning, while also highlighting how personal and educational backgrounds influence students' entrepreneurial orientation. They further offer valuable insights for understanding similar dynamics in the Angolan context.

This research is aimed to determine if:

1. There is a significant relationship between gender, working experience, father's occupation, mother's occupation, and entrepreneurial inclination.
2. Entrepreneurship factors, namely the university's role in promoting entrepreneurship, an entrepreneurial curriculum, and relevant content, have a significant relationship with entrepreneurial inclination.

As such, the following null hypotheses were tested:

Ho1: Gender has no significant relationship to entrepreneurial inclination.

Ho2: Working Experience has no significant relationship to entrepreneurial inclination.

Ho3: Father's Occupation has no significant relationship to entrepreneurial inclination.

Ho4: Mother's Occupation has no significant relationship to entrepreneurial inclination.

Ho5: university's role to promote entrepreneurship has no significant relationship to entrepreneurial inclination.

Ho6: The Entrepreneurial curriculum and content have no significant relationship to entrepreneurial inclination

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive and quantitative research design to examine the demographic profile, family background, perceptions of entrepreneurial factors, and entrepreneurial inclination of Angolan students studying in the Philippines. The quantitative component sought to identify the extent and nature of relationships between demographic variables, family background, entrepreneurship-related factors, and entrepreneurial inclination.

Population and Sampling

The study population consisted of 56 Angolan business students enrolled in Philippine universities. According to the Angolan Embassy, a total of 187 Angolan students studied in the Philippines between 2010 and 2018. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select respondents, while the selection of schools followed a random sampling approach. The study included Angolan students enrolled in business programs and residing in Batangas, Pangasinan, Cavite, Manila, Baguio, and Vigan.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured and standardized questionnaire adapted from Keat and Selvarajah (2011). The self-administered questionnaire was distributed via Google Forms, sent through email and Messenger to respondents in the identified cities. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation analysis.

Research Instrument

The questionnaire consisted of two main parts:

- Part I: Demographic and background information (gender, work experience, father's and mother's occupation). Work experience was measured in years.
- Part II: Entrepreneurship-related factors, including the university's role in promoting entrepreneurship (16 items), the entrepreneurial curriculum and content (10 items), and entrepreneurial inclination (13 items).

Responses were measured using a six-point Likert scale

1 – Strongly Disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Moderately Disagree, 4 – Moderately Agree, 5 – Agree, 6 – Strongly Agree.

A pre-test conducted among 30 Angolan business students yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.85, indicating good internal consistency.

Ethical considerations

Ethical standards were observed throughout the study. Participants were informed of the research's purpose, assured of anonymity and confidentiality, and made aware of their right to withdraw at any time. They were also informed that the results would be used solely for scholarly purposes.

Table 1. Reliability tests for all the variables

Variable	Cronbach Alpha
Entrepreneurship Inclination	.761
University’s role to promote entrepreneurship	.703
Entrepreneurial curriculum and content	.839
Overall	.794

Table 1 indicates that all variables are reliable, with Cronbach’s alpha values of 0.7 or above.

Table 2. Response Categories in the Questionnaire

Scale in the Questionnaire	Numerical value assigned
Strongly Disagree	1
Disagree	2
Moderately Disagree	3
Moderately Agree	4
Agree	5
Strongly Agree	6

Data obtained from the questionnaires were initially encoded in Microsoft Excel and subsequently analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The collected data were organized, tallied, and interpreted using a range of descriptive and inferential statistical tools, including frequency, percentage, mean, and the Chi-square test, all aligned with the study’s objectives. Further statistical analyses were conducted in SPSS at an alpha level of 0.05 to determine the significance of relationships among variables. The Pearson correlation coefficient was employed to assess the strength and direction of relationships between entrepreneurial inclination and selected variables. The interpretation of mean values is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Mean Result Interpretations

Range	Level of EI and URPE and ECC
1.00 – 1.49	Very Low
1.50 – 2.49	Low
2.50 - 3.49	Moderately Low
3.50 - 4.49	Neutral
4.50 – 5.49	Moderately High
5.50 – 6.49	Very High
6.50 - 7.00	

RESULTS

The respondents’ profiles, based on 56 usable questionnaires, showed that females were moderately favored (58.9%) compared to males (41.1%). As all of the respondents were studying at the undergraduate level, they were mostly aged between 18 to 25 years old. When it comes to the respondents’ working experiences, (7.1%) have had 2-3 years working experience, (8.9%) had 4 years of working experience, and 83.9% have had no work experience. About the respondents’ parents’ working status, most of their fathers have been fixed working as (employed) (67.9%) and (1.8%) are driver, (14.3%) are self-employed, (1.8%) are in between jobs, (7.1%) are unemployed, (5.4%) already passed away, (1.8%) are farmer. Their mothers who were fixed working as (employed) with (41.1%), (23.2%) are self-employed, (5.4%) are in between jobs, (21.4%) are unemployed, (7.1%) are housewives, (1.8%) are midwives.

Table 4. Demographics of Respondents

Demographics	Groupings	Respondents N= 56	
		Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	23	41.1%
	Female	33	58.9%
Working experience	0-1 year	47	83.9%
	2-3 year	4	7.1%
	4 years and above	5	8.9%

Father's occupation	Employed	38	67.9%
	Driver	1	1.8%
	Self-employed	8	14.3%
	In-between jobs	1	1.8%
	Unemployed	4	7.1%
	Passed away	3	5.4%
	Farmer	1	1.8%
Mother's occupation	Employed	23	41.1%
	self-employed	13	23.2%
	In-between jobs	3	5.4%
	Unemployed	12	21.4%
	Housewife	4	7.1%
	Midwife	1	1.8%

Regarding entrepreneurial inclination, the data indicate that most students expressed a strong desire to make a positive impact on society, with Item 9 obtaining the highest mean score ($M = 5.09$). Students acknowledged that starting a business is challenging, yet achievable through faith, encouragement, and perseverance. Items 1 and 5, which state that students consider entrepreneurship a highly desirable career option and would like to start their own business someday, both recorded a mean score of 5.04, reflecting a high level of entrepreneurial aspiration. These findings suggest that entrepreneurship is viewed as an attractive and attainable career path among the respondents. Conversely, Item 8, which states that students prefer to work in a large organization rather than a small firm, received the lowest mean score ($M = 2.93$), indicating that the majority favor working in smaller firms or owning their own businesses.

Table 5 Entrepreneurial Inclination

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I seriously consider entrepreneurship as a highly desirable career option.	5.04	Moderately High
2. I never thought of entrepreneurship as a career choice.	3.91	Neutral
3. I Have the plan for opening a new venture	4.34	Neutral
4. I won't start a business because it is too risky and I am afraid of failing.	4.64	Moderately High
5. I Would like someday to start my own business.	5.04	Moderately High
6. I Could easily pursue a career involving self-employment.	4.59	Moderately High
7. If pursue a career involving self-employment the chances of failure would be every high.	3.98	Neutral
8. I prefer to work in a big organization rather than a small firm.	2.93	Moderately Low
9. I want to attain a better position in society.	5.09	Moderately High
10. Entrepreneurship is the future from of employment.	4.91	Moderately High
11. I want to develop my hobby into business.	4.93	Moderately High
12. A career as entrepreneur is attractive for me.	4.70	Moderately High
13. Entrepreneurship is for people who have courage and ideas.	4.59	Moderately High
Composite Mean of Entrepreneurial Inclination	4.51	Moderately High

Regarding the respondents' perceptions of the university's role in promoting entrepreneurship, the results indicate that students strongly believe the university plays a significant role in influencing their decision to start a business ($M = 4.20$).

Table 6 The university's role to promote entrepreneurship

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. University is an ideal place to learn about starting a business.	4.59	Moderately High
2. More entrepreneurship and business educational programmers on campus would help students to start businesses.	4.57	Moderately High
3. Entrepreneurial or business related examples are included in classroom teaching.	4.52	Moderately High
4. Students are encouraged to pursue entrepreneurship ventures in the university.	4.68	Moderately High

5. The university infrastructure and policies encourage entrepreneurship.	2.70	Moderately Low
6. Get to meet lots of people with good ideas for new businesses.	4.80	Moderately High
7. People are actively encouraged to pursue their own business ideas.	4.55	Moderately High
8. My university course prepares people well for entrepreneurial careers.	4.84	Moderately High
9. There are student clubs on campus which promote entrepreneurship.	3.21	Moderately Low
10. University has infrastructure in place to support the start-up of new businesses	4.09	Neutral
11. A creative university environment inspires me to develop ideas for new business.	4.34	Neutral
12. Entrepreneurial activities are for every students.	2.46	Moderately Low
13. Entrepreneurship courses should be made compulsory in order to stimulate entrepreneurial spirit in campus.	4.39	Neutral
14. The university provides resources to assist student entrepreneurs.	4.29	Neutral
15. At my university, I get to meet lots of people with good ideas for new business.	4.46	Neutral
16. My university has an atmosphere that inspires and encourages entrepreneurship.	4.41	Neutral
Composite Mean URPE	4.20	Neutral

The findings reveal that the entrepreneurial curriculum and content strongly reflect students’ perceived ability to succeed in entrepreneurship. The curriculum is designed to enhance students’ knowledge, skills, and competencies relevant to entrepreneurial practice. This dimension obtained a moderately high mean score (M = 4.82), as shown in Table 7, indicating that students recognize the curriculum’s positive impact on their entrepreneurial development.

Table 7: The entrepreneurial curriculum and content

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. The instructors are experienced and competent course presenters.	4.54	Moderately High
2. As a result of taking this course, have better understanding about business.	4.82	Moderately High
3. The instructor did a good job of making this course relevant to the real world.	4.73	Moderately High
4. The course developed entrepreneurial knowledge and skills.	4.89	Moderately High
5. The instructor did stimulate interest in entrepreneurship through the course(s).	4.71	Moderately High
6. Interest towards entrepreneurship has been raised after taking the course(s).	4.82	Moderately High
7. The course(s) provided a new and different experience.	4.98	Moderately High
8. The course(s) taught to deal with ambiguity in the real world.	4.88	Moderately High
9. The course(s) provided an opportunity to learn by doing.	5.16	Moderately High
10. The course(s) provided the opportunity to do things my ways without conforming to formal class structures.	4.66	Moderately High
Composite Mean ECC	4.82	Moderately High

The analysis examined the relationship between gender, work experience, father’s occupation, and mother’s occupation and students’ entrepreneurial inclination. Results revealed that none of these variables were significantly related to entrepreneurial inclination (Kaygisiz. 2015). (see Table 8). This indicates that students’ inclination toward entrepreneurship is independent of gender, prior work experience, and parental occupation. Thus, the null hypothesis—that these variables do not significantly influence entrepreneurial inclination—was accepted. These findings are consistent with those of Kristiansen and Nurul Indarti (2004), who found that gender had no significant impact on entrepreneurial inclination among students from Indonesia and Norway. Similarly, Shinnar et al. (2009) reported no significant difference in entrepreneurial interest between male and female students. Furthermore, Lebbaeus Asamani and Abigail Opoku Mensah (2013) and Ooi Yeng Keat (2011) also found no significant relationship between work experience or parental occupation and entrepreneurial inclination. The absence of gender-based differences in this study may be attributed to the fact that both male and female respondents share similar cultural backgrounds and socialization experiences, leading to comparable attitudes toward entrepreneurship (Edirisinghe & Nimeshi, 2016).

Table 8: Relationship of gender, working experience, father’s occupation and mother’s occupation to entrepreneurial inclination.

Variable	Entrepreneurial Inclination x ² [p-value]	Interpretation
Gender	28.455 [.287]	Not Significant
Working Experience	39.974 [.844]	Not Significant
Father’s Occupation	171.827 [.107]	Not Significant
Mother’s Occupation	138.169 [.198]	Not Significant

Table 9 presents the relationship between the university’s role in promoting entrepreneurship (URPE) and the entrepreneurial curriculum and content (ECC) with students’ entrepreneurial inclination. The results indicate that the URPE is not significantly related to students’ entrepreneurial inclination ($r = 0.136, p = 0.319$), whereas the ECC shows a significant positive relationship with entrepreneurial inclination ($r = 0.297, p = 0.026$). Although both correlations are positive—suggesting that improvements in either variable may enhance entrepreneurial inclination—the strength of association differs.

Specifically, the URPE demonstrates an insignificant and very weak positive correlation, implying that while the university environment contributes marginally, it does not strongly predict students’ entrepreneurial tendencies. In contrast, the ECC exhibits a significant but weak positive correlation, indicating that a more comprehensive and practical entrepreneurial curriculum is associated with a higher level of entrepreneurial inclination among students. These findings suggest that curriculum design, content delivery, and institutional promotion efforts play a more influential role in fostering entrepreneurial orientation than institutional promotion efforts alone.

Table 9: Relationship of the university’s role to promote entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial curriculum and content to entrepreneurial inclination.

Variable	Entrepr. Inclination	Teurial Interpretation
Universian ty Role to Promote Entrepreneurship	r-value .136 p-value .319	Positive, very weak Not Significant
Entrepreneurial Curriculum and Content	r-value .297* p-value .026	Positive, weak Significant

**Significant at .05 level*

The analysis of the data basis for the research questions and hypotheses.

Ho1: Gender has no significant relationship to entrepreneurial inclination.

Ho2: Working Experience has no significant relationship to entrepreneurial inclination.

Ho3: Father’s Occupation has no significant relationship to entrepreneurial inclination.

Ho4: Mother’s Occupation has no significant relationship to entrepreneurial inclination.

Ho5: university’s role to promote entrepreneurship has no significant relationship to entrepreneurial inclination.

From Ho1 to Ho5, failed to reject the null hypothesis, which concludes that there is not enough evidence at the α (.05) level to conclude that there is a linear relationship among the variables.

Ho6: Entrepreneurial curriculum and content have no significant relationship to entrepreneurial inclination.

The Entrepreneurial Curriculum and Content (ECC) rejects the null hypothesis, indicating that there is sufficient evidence at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level to support a linear relationship between ECC attributes and students’ entrepreneurial inclination. Specifically, Pearson’s correlation analysis (Table 9) demonstrates a positive association between ECC attributes and entrepreneurial inclination ($r = 0.297, p < 0.026$). These findings are consistent with Lewicka (2011), who reported that individuals with entrepreneurial inclination typically exhibit self-confidence, an internal locus of control, innovative behaviors, a propensity for risk-taking, leadership qualities, and a readiness to engage in teamwork. Leadership, in particular, is a critical component of entrepreneurship, as the ability to articulate a vision and sustain motivation is essential for success in the business environment.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to examine whether Angolan students’ entrepreneurial inclination is influenced by demographic factors, the university’s role in promoting entrepreneurship, and the entrepreneurial curriculum and content. This suggests that students possess a strong capacity to understand and evaluate their own perceptions of entrepreneurship. The findings indicate that demographic factors do not significantly influence entrepreneurial inclination. Conversely, both the university’s role in promoting entrepreneurship and the entrepreneurial curriculum and content were positively correlated with students’ entrepreneurial inclination, with the entrepreneurial curriculum and content demonstrating the greatest impact on the entrepreneurial tendencies of Angolan students.

Specifically, demographic factors were found to have no significant effect on entrepreneurial inclination, a finding consistent with Asamani and Opoku Mensah (2013) in their study of Ghanaian university students. In contrast, Mahajar (2012) and Ooi Keat (2011) reported that demographic factors have a strong relationship with entrepreneurial inclination. The university’s role in promoting entrepreneurship exhibited a

weak positive correlation with entrepreneurial inclination. This aligns with the findings of Asamani and Mensah (2013) and Mahajar (2012), although Ooi Keat (2011) argued that the university's role plays a crucial role in shaping students' entrepreneurial orientation. Additionally, the study confirmed a positive correlation between entrepreneurial curriculum and content and entrepreneurial inclination, consistent with the observations of Asamani and Mensah (2013), Mahajar (2012), and Ooi Keat (2011).

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that both the university's role in promoting entrepreneurship and its entrepreneurial curriculum and content (ECC) are positively correlated with students' entrepreneurial inclination. Based on these findings, several conclusions can be drawn. Demographic factors, including gender, work experience, father's occupation, and mother's occupation, were found to have no statistically significant influence on students' entrepreneurial inclination. Regarding the university's role in promoting entrepreneurship, elements such as educational programs on campus, the overall university environment, and institutional encouragement demonstrated a notable, though limited, impact on students' entrepreneurial tendencies.

Pearson correlation analysis served as the basis for examining the relationships between the variables and testing the research hypotheses (Ho5 and Ho6). Hypothesis Ho5 posited that the university's role in promoting entrepreneurship (URPE) has no influence on students' entrepreneurial inclination (EI). The results indicated that this hypothesis could not be rejected, suggesting a limited effect of URPE on EI. In contrast, hypothesis Ho6 proposed that the entrepreneurial curriculum and content (ECC) significantly influences students' entrepreneurial inclination. Correlation analysis results supported this hypothesis, with ECC demonstrating a statistically significant positive effect on entrepreneurial inclination, as indicated by the corresponding r and p values.

Furthermore, ECC courses provide students with experiential learning opportunities, fostering the development of entrepreneurial knowledge and skills. These courses also provide students with novel experiences that help them navigate ambiguity and complexity in real-world entrepreneurial contexts.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the study, it was recommended that the professors use the university curriculum to enhance the students' learning capacity and have a strong inclination to entrepreneurship. It is also suggested that schools in the Philippines improve by providing a better learning approach to students for better education and training.

LIMITATIONS

In light of the limitations of this research, it is recommended that future researchers further explore the university's role in promoting entrepreneurship and developing an entrepreneurial curriculum and content. Results will provide further insight into the university's role in promoting entrepreneurship (URPE) and entrepreneurial curriculum and content (ECC) concepts, thereby enriching the existing body of knowledge. These variables have shown the influence on students' inclination to pursue a certain field. Furthermore, the population sample was limited. Hence, we suggest a diverse population sample.

NOTE

This study is a master's thesis authored by Paula Matilde Lourenço Abel, defended in 2018 at De La Salle University, Lipa. It has not been published in any journal. With the guidance of Professor Edivaldo Abel, the thesis was reformatted and edited to meet the publication requirements of the *Journal of Social Science and Human Research Studies*.

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